

**FACTORS HAMPERING ON PHOTOGRAPHIC IMAGE
REPRESENTATION OF CHILD ABUSE FOR TEACHING JUNIOR
SECONDARY SCHOOL IN EMOHUA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA**

¹Dr. Ugochukwu Kingsley Nwombu and ²Okwelle Elizabeth

¹Department of Fine & Applied Arts, Faculty of Humanities²Ignatius Ajuru University of Education,
Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt

Emails: ugochukwu.nwombu@iaue.edu.ng, okwelleelizabeth@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8249215>

Abstract: This study centers on the factors hampering on photographic image representation of child abuse for teaching junior secondary school in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. One research question and one null hypothesis guided the conduct of the study. The study adopted the correlational and Ex-post facto research Design; on a population that comprised all final year students of 2019/2020 academic session offering visual arts as a subject of study in the schools mentioned above. The total number of students in the population is 130. The entire population was studied. A structured questionnaire with 25 items was used to generate data from the respondents titled ‘impact of photographic images of child abuse as instructional materials (IMPHICAIM)’. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. The Cronbach Alpha reliability technique obtained reliability indexes of .80, .88, .90, .73 and .78 respectively for each sub-scale. Then, Data on students’ academic performance was extracted from the students’ academic records; students were also interviewed on their experiences while on the training. Data collected were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to answer the research questions as well as testing the hypothesis that determine the degree of association between the variables under consideration. The result indicates that photographic image representation of child abuse has a positive correlation as instructional materials relevant to teaching students in junior secondary schools. Therefore, there is a significant correlation between the factors hampering photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional materials for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. It is recommended that teachers design effective child abuse photographs as instructional materials to teach students in secondary schools in Emohua local government Area.

Keywords: Factors hampering, Photographic image, Child abuse, Teaching JSS

INTRODUCTION

Instructional materials are pedagogical aid which enables instruction to be meaningful to learner, due to the role of representing the idea in question in visible form. It makes it real for understanding to take place and knowledge to be formed. It is also known as teaching learning materials (TLM) and are any collection of materials of animate and inanimate objects and human and non-human resources that a teacher may use in teaching and learning

situations to help achieve desired learning objectives. It may aid a student in concretizing an interactive session. They are tools used in instructional activities, which include active learning and assessment (Lewis, 2018). According to (IGI Global, 2019), instructional materials refer to the human and non-human materials and facilities that can be used to ease, encourage, improve and promote teaching and learning activities. Agina-Obu (2005) advocates that while designing or using instructional materials, it should be learner or child centered and not teacher because they are meant to help the learner learn better. Instructional material can be used to teach all topics including child abuse in the school system.

Over the years, every society has continuously been challenged by cases of child abuse. Although the form of abuse has changed over time, those continuous cases of child abuse have implications on the sustainable development of the child in particular and the society in general. The consequences of this abuse on the child suggests that the perpetuation of those heinous acts does not only deny the child the pleasure of developing at his/her expected rate of growth but rather forces him/her to experience mental, emotional and physical challenges. In Emohua Local Government Area, child abuse has continued to be a menace in every community and this can be attributed to the economic situation that has seen families compromise the future of their children in a bid to survive as well as the failure of legal institutions established by the government to protect children (Ariston, 2009; Faruk; 2015, Fielding, 2016 and Kubanni, 2019). As a result of this predicament where children are abused by working at tender age, the children are exposed to possible accidents, harmful situations such as pedophiles, kidnappers and drug peddlers. Ebigbo, (2006) opines that child abuse acts such as child trafficking has seen children engage in under age sex, thereby exposing them to the risk of Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STD). This consequently poses a threat to the society because the increase in prevalence of sexually transmitted diseases for children has the potential to reduce the average life expectancy of that society thereby disrupting sustainable development. According to Olaitan & Amos (2016), parents also marry off their daughters at an early age in most cases to improve the economic conditions of the family without considering the impact it will have on the child emotionally and physically in terms of early child bearing, dropping out of school and impaired development. Physically, abused children experience various undesired consequences, ranging from soft tissue injuries to death from unknown causes, loss in memory, growth retardation, speech delay, social withdrawal, limited friends and peer relationship, academic challenges, suicidal tendencies as well as interpersonal cognitive, emotional and behavioral problems (Russell, 2018 & Tolmachev, 2019). Several studies have been carried out by scholars and authors on photographic images and that of child abuse which has expanded literature on the above concepts, yet none of the studies was done on the factors hampering on photographic image representation of child abuse as instructional material in teaching students in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria

Emohua is one of the local government areas in Rivers State of Nigeria that witnessed child abuse cases. The people's major occupation is predominantly farming, fishing and trading. One of the means through which they practice their major occupation is farming. It has been observed that some children of school age are trading their education with farming by following their parents to farm. Child abuse constitutes all forms of physical, emotional ill-treatment, neglect, sexual abuse and commercial or other exploitations that result in actual or potential harm to the child's health, survival, development or dignity in context of a relationship or responsibilities, trust or power, (World Health Organization, 2016: p. 9). The organization condemned child abuse by describing it as abnormal failure to give attention or care to children under parental jurisdiction either by birth or adoption from established welfare organization. These among other reasons has made this study imperative.

Aim and Objective of the Study

The aim of the study is to identify the factors hampering on photographic images representation of child abuse as instructional material for teaching students in junior secondary school in Emohua Local Government Area.

Research Question

What are the factors hampering on photographic image representations of child abuse as instructional materials relevant to teaching students in junior secondary school in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant correlation between the factors hampering photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional materials for teaching in junior secondary school in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Significance of the Study

The study helped to create photographic image representation of child abuse that would be used for teaching in junior secondary school as instructional materials. It has contributed to the knowledge bank of instructional materials for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area in Rivers State.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study was delimited to the public junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. It was as well, delimited to the use of photographic image representation of child abuse as instructional material to teach students in junior secondary school in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Definition of Terms / Abbreviations

- 1) TLM - Teaching Learning Materials
- 2) STD – Sexually Transmitted Disease
- 3) WHO – World Health Organization
- 4) S-R-C – Stimulus Response Connection
- 5) AFRUCA – Africa Unite Against Child Abuse
- 6) Pivot – Centre point on which something balance
- 7) SKILL – Ability to do something well because you have learned
- 8) PPMC – Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Literature Review – An Overview of Instructional Material

Instructional materials refers to those alternative channels of USCDCP – United States Centres for Disease Control and Prevention communication, which a classroom teacher can use to concretize a concept during teaching and learning process (Mayer, 2005: p 1-16). Traditionally, classroom teachers have relied heavily on the 'talk-chalk' method during their teaching. But recently, instructional materials help to provide variations in the ways in which messages are sent across. In using instructional materials, teachers and students do not only extend the range of sense organs we use but also extend the range of materials used for conveying the same message through the same organ. For instance, in teaching a topic a teacher can manipulate real objects or use their stimulators. Instructional materials therefore constitute the media of exchange through which a message transaction is facilitated between a source and a receiver. In addition to extending the range of materials that can be used to convey the same instructional message to learners' instructional materials also facilitate the 'process' nature of communication. In this passage, the nature of communication 'process' implies that both the source and

the receiver of a message are actively involved in a communication encounter. It means that both the receiver and the source share and exchange ideas, feelings in any communication (Achuonye, & Ajoku, 2003; Agina-Obu, 2005; Umobong, 2010; & Sadiq 2013; Kubanni, 2019).

Instructional materials are print and non-print items that are vested to impact information to students in the educational process. Instructional materials include items such as: kits, textbooks, magazines, newspapers, pictures, recording videos etc. Instructional materials play a very important role in the teaching and learning process. (Clark, L., & Starr, 1995). The authors also cited the views of other authors as follows: It enhances the memory level of the students. At this time that education has spread wide and entirely, oral teaching cannot be the key to successful pedagogy; therefore the teacher has to use instructional materials to make teaching and learning process interesting (NIC hulls, 2003; Raw, 2006) . Instructional materials are tools locally made or imported that help to facilitate the teaching/learning process. Materials things which are used to composed instructional materials that could make tremendous enhancement of intellectual property of a learner. The use of instructional materials can enhance the learning achievement. The important elements of behaviour that provides the base for learning theory situation which consists of all the objects, persons and symbols in the learning environment. Experience in situation prepares a person to respond to similar situation in future. Use of instructional materials can appeal to the individual attention by creating interest goal that will help the learner achieve direct effort. Teacher's problem of motivation is essentially one of arranging situation with instructional materials in which the learner will see goals he wants to attain. Brown et al (2005) summarized the role of teaching aids as follows:

1. It promotes meaningful communication and effective learning.
2. They ensure better retention, thus making learning more permanent
3. They help to overcome the limited classroom by making the inaccessible accessible
4. They provide a common experience upon which late learning can be developed. They stimulate and motivate students to learn.
5. They encourage participation especially if students are allowed to manipulate materials used. Osuala (2010) in his own contribution said it does not only help to motivate and develop interest on the part of the student, but also help to bring about an enhance respect for teachers' knowledge of the subject. Instructional materials are also described as concrete or both to the sense organs during teaching (Aginna-Obu 2000; Wikipedia Free Readers Encyclopaedia, 2016).

Research Methodology

The research method adopted for this study is the correlational and Ex-post facto research Design; on a population that comprised all final year students of 2019/2020 academic session offering visual arts as a subject of study in the mentioned above. The total number of students in the population is 130. The entire population was studied. A structured questionnaire with 25 items was used to generate data from the respondents titled 'Impact of Photographic Images of Child Abuse as Instructional Materials (IMPHICAIM)'. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. The Cronbach Alpha reliability technique obtained reliability indexes of .80, .88, .90, .73 and .78 respectively for each sub-scale. Then, Data on students' academic performance was extracted from the students' academic records; students were also interviewed on their experiences while in their studies. Data collected were analysed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to answer the research questions

as well as testing the hypothesis that determine the degree of association between the variables under consideration.

Plate 1: Rejected

Photograph size (20cmx16cm)

© Okelle, Elizabeth 2019

Husband rejects wife for given birth to female quadruplet and drove them out of home. Says, she has brought poverty to the home. A wicked society! The woman resolved to taken the children to the road for succor.

Presentation of Data and Discussion

Answering of Research Question

Research Question One: To what extent are photographic image representation of child abuse as instructional materials relevant to teaching students in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 1: Summary of relationship test between photographic image representation of child abuse and teaching students

Variables	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r_{cal}
Photographic images of child abuse	1942	5790	9546	0.310
Teaching students	3428	17084		

The result from Table 1 shows the summary of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) of the relationship between photographic image representation of child abuse as instructional materials relevant to teaching students in Junior Secondary Schools in Emohua Local Government Area. The result of the analysis shows an r-value of 0.310. This indicates that photographic image representation of child abuse has a positive correlation as instructional materials relevant to teaching students in junior secondary schools.

Testing of Null Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significant correlation between the factors hampering photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional materials for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 2: Summary of PPMC significant relationship test between factors hampering photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional materials for teaching

Variables	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r_{cal}	Df	r_{crit}	Decision
Factors hampering photographic image representation of child abuse	1715	4445	8171	0.601	698	0.139	Reject Null Hypothesis
Instructional materials for teaching	3347	16303					

Significant @ .05 alpha level

The result from Table 2 shows that with a df of 698 and at 0.05 level of significance, the critical value of r (0.139) is less than the calculated value of r (0.601). This means that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant correlation between the factors hampering photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional materials for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

There is a significant correlation between the impact of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional materials for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Correlation between the Impact of Photographic Image Representation of Child Abuse and Instructional Materials for Teaching in Junior Secondary Schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

The result of hypothesis one at 0.05 level of significance and with a df of 698, the calculated value of r (0.310) is greater than the critical value of r (0.139). This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, therefore, there is a significant correlation between the impact of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional materials for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. The findings of the study support the views of Roberson (2012) that the use of graphic visuals as instructional material is very important because it motives learners. This fact shows a correlation between photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional materials for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

References

- Agina-Obu, T.N. (2005). *The Relevance of Instructional Materials in Teaching and Learning*. In Robert – Okahi, I. & Uzoeshi, GK. *Theory and Practice of Teaching*. Harey Publication.
- Ariston, A.E. (2009). Illustration and Photography in Design Basics. <https://www.cengage.com/art/book-content/04950006939-armstrongdb.se/cho-key.tml>
- Clark, L., & Starr, L. (1996). *Secondary and Middle School Teaching Methods*. New York: Macmillan Publishers.
- Faruk, I. (2015). Impact of Graphics on Academic Performance of Junior Secondary School Students in Jigawa State.
- Fielding, E. (2016). How is Photography Used and What is Its Importance? url. <https://www.quora.com/How-is-photography-used-and-what-is-its-importance>.
- Kubanni (2019) <Http://Kubanni.Abu.Edu.Ng/Jspui/Bitstream/123456789/1/Impact> of Graphic on Academic Performance of Junior Secondary School Students in Social Students In Jigawa State % 2c Nigeria.
- IGI Global. (2019). What is Instructional Materials. <Https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/relevance-of-the-use-of-instructional-materials-and-pedagogical-delivery/48956?-e-pi-=7%2cPAGE-ID10%2c203330521>
- IGI Global (2019). What is Teaching <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/broadcasting-transforming-social-construction-knowledge/29344>
- Lindsay, V. (1913). “Euclid” (in Monroe, Harnet (Ed). *Poetry: A magazine of verse*, 2 (p. 123).
- Mayer, R.E. (2005). Introduction to multimedia learning in R. Mayer (Ed.), *Cambridge handbook of multimedia learning* (p.1-16). New York. Cambridge university press.
- Merriam-W. (2019). Definition of Photography. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/photography>.
- Ross, S. (1996). “Risk of physical abuse to children of spouse abusing parents” *Child Abuse and neglect*, 20(7), 589 – 598 doi: 10.1016/0145-2134(96)00046-4” PMID 8832115k.
- Russell, T. (2018). What Does Photography Mean to You? Why is Its Important?<https://www.quora.com/How-is-photography-used-and-what-is-its-importance>.
- Sadiq, M. (2013). Use of Photographic as a Powerful Tool in Teaching /Learning Environment. An Experience <http://library.iated.org/view/SADIQ2013> USE.
- Tolmachev, I. (2019). A Brief History of Photography: The Beginning <https://photography.tutsplus.com/article/a-history-of-photography-part-i-the-beginning-photo-1908>.

Umobong, M.E. (2010). Child Abuse and its implications for the educational sector in Nigeria.

Wikipedia Free Readers Encyclopedia (2016). Photography Available from Google Cache of <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/photography>.

Wikipedia, Free Reader Encyclopedia (2019) Picture. Available from Google Cache of <http://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/pictureaccessed>.

Wikipedia, the Free Encyclopedia (2019) *Graphic Communication*. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Graphic-communication>.

Wikipedia, Tie Free Encyclopedia (2019) History of Photography. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History-of-photography>.

World Health Organization (2016). Child Abuse and Neglect by Parents and Child.